

Preliminary Evidence From an Original Study Suggests Combustion, Not Nicotine, Drives Risk and Complications of Graves' Orbitopathy

Matteo Acanfora ^{1,2}, Alberto Vassallo ^{3,2}

Review began 08/12/2025

Review ended 08/27/2025

Published 08/28/2025

© Copyright 2025

Acanfora et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License CC-BY 4.0., which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI: 10.7759/cureus.91181

1. Institute of Endocrine and Metabolic Sciences, Istituto di Ricovero e Cura a Carattere Scientifico (IRCCS) Ospedale San Raffaele, Milan, ITA 2. Endocrinology Unit, Vita-Salute San Raffaele University, Milan, ITA 3. Institute of Endocrine and Metabolic Sciences, Istituto di Ricovero e Cura a Carattere Scientifico (IRCCS) Ospedale San Raffaele, Milan, ITA

Corresponding author: Matteo Acanfora, acanfora.matteo@hsr.it

Abstract

Introduction

Graves' orbitopathy (GO) is a significant complication of Graves' disease (GD), often exacerbated by cigarette smoking. While smoking is a well-established risk factor, it remains unclear whether nicotine itself or toxic combustion byproducts are primarily responsible. Here, we present preliminary results from our study, which investigates the impact of different nicotine delivery systems on GO features and clinical outcomes.

Methods

We retrospectively analyzed 304 adult patients with newly diagnosed GD. Patients were categorized based on nicotine exposure: combustible cigarette users (CSU), heated tobacco product users (HTPU), electronic cigarette users (ECU), and never-nicotine users (NNU). Statistical comparisons were performed to evaluate any significant difference across groups.

Results

GO prevalence was highest in CSU (n=31, 50.1%) and significantly lower in HTPU (n=8, 26.7%), NNU (n=40, 21.1%), and ECU (n=2, 8.7%). No moderate-to-severe or active GO cases were found among ECUs. Logistic regression confirmed CSU as an independent risk factor for GO (OR=4.02; p<0.001).

Discussion

These preliminary findings suggest how tobacco combustion byproducts, rather than nicotine itself, may be the key drivers of GO pathogenesis. The low GO prevalence in ECUs supports the hypothesis that clean nicotine delivery might carry reduced or no risk.

Conclusion

Combustible tobacco use is strongly associated with GO risk, while non-combustion systems, especially ECs, might offer a safer alternative. These results will be implemented with final analyses of the study, and encourage further investigation into harm-reduction strategies in patients with GD.

Categories: Internal Medicine, Ophthalmology, Endocrinology/Diabetes/Metabolism.

Keywords: e-cigarettes, graves' disease, graves' orbitopathy, heated-tobacco-products, nicotine, smoke.

How to cite this article

Acanfora M, Vassallo A (August 28, 2025) Preliminary Evidence From an Original Study Suggests Combustion, Not Nicotine, Drives Risk and Complications of Graves' Orbitopathy. *Cureus* 17(8): e91181. DOI 10.7759/cureus.91181